

Dynamic process simulations and control of a lignite/waste to Fischer Tropsch liquids plant

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Abstract:

This study comprises the dynamic process simulations of a HTW gasification plant for Fischer-Tropsch (FT) liquids production under transient feedstock of lignite and solid recovered fuel (SRF) as well as load variations. Main objective of the current study is the proof of concept in unsteady conditions and the effective plant wide control of a novel gasification-driven liquid fuels production pathway. Therefore, the dynamic analysis of all sub-units in an integrated simulation scheme by means of Aspen Plus Dynamics (APD) and MATLAB/Simulink interference is attempted. In this way, it is possible to evaluate the impact of system disturbances on every process stage and apply the required control strategies to ensure system stability. Another aspect addressed within this work is the alternative management of solid materials in APD environment, which is an inherent drawback of this otherwise appropriate software as mentioned in previous studies. The performed dynamic simulations revealed that the proposed value chain seems to have a respectable potential in terms of operational flexibility and performance stability, always in relation to the gasification-based chemical plants and the constraints that accompany them.

Keywords: dynamic simulations, plant-wide control, lignite/SRF HTW gasification, Fischer-Tropsch liquids, Aspen Plus Dynamics

1 Introduction

Depletion of fossil fuel energy resources is one of the most notable challenges of the 21st century. Moreover, as the signs of the climate change and global warming become more alarming, a rapid transition towards renewables energy systems along with elimination of the carbon footprint in energy-intensive industries (e.g. transportation) seem essential [1]. Even though electrification can lead to a significant reduction of GHG emissions, sustainable solutions such as low-carbon or non-fossil drop-in fuels, that offer instant compliance with the existing infrastructure, are in a favorable position towards the targeted decarbonization.

Gasification-based pathways have been widely elected as an efficient way to convert carbonaceous materials into a synthesis gas (syngas) that may be subsequently converted via multiple routes into synthetic transport fuels [2]. Perhaps the most common route is the Fischer-Tropsch (FT) synthesis, which refers to the catalytic conversion of syngas to parafins. Fischer-Tropsch synthesis can use syngas derived from any source including coal, biomass or natural gas and it can produce precursors for a wide range of drop-in chemicals and fuels [3]. The more sustainable is the initial feedstock that enters the gasification unit, the lower is the carbon footprint of the emerged FT liquid fuels. The

co-gasification of fossil fuels (i.e. coal/lignite) and sustainable fuels (i.e. biomass/wastes) is a quite new scheme that ends up in low-carbon liquid FT-fuels production by reducing fossil CO₂ emissions and exploiting waste materials. The latter concept is investigated in the European project Lig2Liq [4] and is also the inspiration of the present study. In particular, the simultaneous valorization of lignite and solid recovered fuel (SRF), by means of the High Temperature Winkler (HTW) gasification technology, integrated into a sustainable Fischer-Tropsch pathway is assessed. SRF is a high-quality waste derived fuel that presents high heating value and is usually prepared into dried pellets or bales [5, 6]. The SRF gasification concepts attract the interest for further industrial development mainly due to the fact that 'wastes-to-energy' schemes do not only open up new possibilities in the immature and disproportionate waste management systems of very waste-productive fields, but also decrease the average feedstock price of the plant [7, 8]. HTW is a fluidized bed gasification technology that is rather more flexible compared to entrained flow reactors, since it can use various types of fuels as additional feedstock, and properly deal with co-gasification constraints (e.g. low ash fusion temperature, noxious interferences, etc.) [9-11].

While steady-state simulations can provide accurate results in specific operating modes of a plant, dynamic simulations can be a more effective tool towards the functionality and optimization of flexible concepts, such as the one proposed within this study, where the feedstock mixture is variable [12]. The main objective of the dynamic simulations performed within this study is to investigate the effect of applied fuel feed fluctuations (from lignite to SRF and vice versa/load variations) in the key unit operations, to assess plant's flexibility and determine the actions that should be taken in order to secure that the desired standards of the liquid fuel production will remain intact. In particular, the feedstock flexibility in the gasifier leads to syngas variations. These variations in the syngas composition usually cause new gas handling requirements, so that the specifications of the fuel synthesis unit (e.g. H₂/CO ratio, organic compounds & contaminants concentrations) are met. Other parameters able to influence the steady operational mode of the plant are the fuel load (i.e. larger/lower fuel flow rates) as well as the temperature and pressure fluctuations of each unit.

While there is a decent amount of literature dealing with the dynamic behavior of each sub-unit separately including valuable studies that have shed light in the non-steady operation of ASU [13-15], gasification [16-21], acid gas removal [22-24] and FT synthesis [25-27], the plant-wide control of such an integrated configuration that investigates the dynamic interaction among the sub-units during feedstock/load variations has not been attempted yet. One of the most common software platforms that are employed to perform the dynamic simulations of such chemical processes is Aspen Plus Dynamics (APD). However, its inability to cope up with models involving solids has lead to alternatives (e.g. MATLAB/Simulink, gPROMs, etc.) for dynamic simulations of processes that have to handle with solid materials (e.g. gasification). Only [21] aimed to perform gasification dynamic simulations with APD using a simplified but effective approach. A similar approach is adopted within the present study in order to overpass the constraints of APD regarding solids and achieve synchronized dynamic simulations of each sub-unit, including gasification, in APD environment.

Therefore, in summary, the present study focuses on the dynamic simulations of a concept based on co-gasification of lignite/SRF that ends up in sustainable FT-liquids. The quite novel aspect of this work is the plant-wide control and parallel dynamic analysis of every sub-unit of the proposed concept (ASU, gasification, gas cleaning & conditioning, FT-synthesis) in an integrated scheme, utilizing the available compatibility of Aspen Plus Dynamics (APD) and MATLAB/Simulink. This combination offers the opportunity to combine the advantages of two different software (i.e. the advanced capabilities of APD in modelling chemical processes and the flexibility offered by MATLAB/Simulink in implementing plant-wide control schemes). Moreover, this study aims to unlock the inherent bottleneck of APD to handle with solids streams by providing

a new approach to investigate a gasification process and obtain reliable results. Every developed dynamic model was validated in selected modes against the steady state heat and mass balances of the process that preceded.

Finally, it has to be mentioned that the main scope of the present dynamic study is the primary evaluation of the plant adaptability in operational fluctuations and the identification of the required measures to achieve system restore according to the desired conditions. Towards this direction, the flow-driven mode of APD, which is appropriate for a first approach of the dynamic behavior of the process, was selected for the performed dynamic simulations. In flow-driven simulations, the flow rates are governed by the assumption of perfect control and are decoupled from the pressure variations. On the other hand, optimal dynamic behavior via a more complex sophisticated control scheme would require the more rigorous pressure-driven mode of APD, in which the flowrates result from pressure difference. However, it has to be noticed that even in the selected flow-driven mode, some blocks are internally pressure-driven and pressure/level controllers are added automatically to ensure pressure/flows consistency [28].

2 Concept description

The proposed concept involves the co-gasification of lignite/SRF via High Temperature Winkler (HTW) gasification for the production of syngas. The latter, after a gas cleaning & conditioning procedure, will be utilized from a fuel synthesis (Fischer-Tropsch) unit for the catalytic generation of a blend of valuable hydrocarbons (FT liquids or FT-crude). A simplified flowsheet of the concept that is investigated within this study is presented below in Figure 1.

Figure 1. Simplified flowsheet of the proposed concept

Solid raw material consisting of solid recovered fuel (SRF) and pre-dried lignite coal is prepared and mixed for feeding into the gasifier and enters the fluidized bed. With the assistance of the gasification agents, oxygen and steam, the solid feed is converted into a raw syngas stream that leaves the reactor from the top. Smaller particles still present in the raw gas are removed in a hot particle filter downstream. The required oxygen is secured from an Air Separation Unit (ASU) that continuously feeds the gasifier with pure oxygen, while the necessary steam is generated from the heat recovery of raw syngas via heat exchangers. Ambient air (78% N₂, 21% O₂ and 1% Ar vol.) is utilized as input stream in the separation process. The main objective of the ASU is to cover the oxygen

requirements of the HTW gasifier in terms of quantity and purity, as well as by response time, from the dynamic point of view.

At the bottom of the fluidized bed ash particles leave the reactor via a sluicing system to form the bottom product. Fly ash entrained with the raw syngas is detached by a cyclone and recycled to the fluidized bed.

After heat recovery and filtering, the raw syngas undergoes a water scrubbing process for cooling and saturation. In the water scrubber, complete removal of HCl along with partial removal of NH₃ and heavier organic compounds are aimed. The syngas is saturated with water and hence cooled down close to saturation temperature. Moreover, in case of defects in the upstream filter system, residual particles remain dissolved in the water. Due to the saturation, process water is consumed by the cooled syngas and fresh demineralized water needs to be added. In order to control the amount of soluble components like chlorides and ammonia, some water is extracted from the circulating water as a bleed stream.

Then, the syngas is sent to the WGS section to adjust the H₂/CO ratio as required to the FT-synthesis (i.e. ~2 on molar basis). A portion of the syngas passes in the CO shift reactor to generate hydrogen, while the amount of bypassed syngas is controlled by a process analyzer downstream of the reactor that ensures the desired H₂/CO ratio in the outlet gas stream. The shifted gas stream and the bypass stream are mixed and routed to the downstream COS hydrolysis reactor, where complete conversion of organic sulphur to H₂S takes place.

A BTX removal unit, based on biodiesel/wash oil, is adopted in order to avoid operational problems from BTX components and naphthalene. The shifted gas is cooled upon which the liquid/medium-volatile tars (e.g. naphthalene) are collected. Then, gaseous tars (e.g. benzene) are absorbed in the scrubbing liquid at the resulting temperature. The liquid tar collection and the gaseous tar absorption are performed in two separate scrubbing columns, i.e. the gas cooler and the absorber. Through intensive contact with the syngas, the wash oil absorbs these hydrocarbon components and is sent for regeneration to the BTX desorber column via heat exchangers for preheating. At the BTX desorber top, the condensable top product is separated from co-absorbed syngas components. After condensation, the top product is separated in the liquid hydrocarbon phase containing BTX and naphthalene and in a second liquid water phase. The water phase is sent to a waste water pre-treatment unit, while the hydrocarbon phase is recycled to the gasification unit.

Within the acid gas removal unit, the acidic components (H₂S & CO₂) are separated from the syngas. These species are removed from the syngas by intensive contact with the amine solution and supported by the extended mass transfer surface provided by structured packings in the absorber column. The rich solvent is reheated by amine solution heat exchangers and routed to the top of the desorber. In the desorber column, CO₂ & H₂S are stripped out of the spent solution by means of water vapour provided by the reboiler attached to the sump of the desorber column. At the top section of the desorber, the water vapour is condensed in the top condenser and separated from the acid gas. The cold acid gas can be sent to a sulphur recovery unit (not modelled in this study). The regenerated solvent leaves the desorber at the bottom and it is cooled against the rich solvent, before it is pumped back to the absorber top.

Downstream of the acid gas removal unit, a final purification stage (e.g. ZnO guard bed) is applied to the syngas prior fuel synthesis unit in order any remaining sulphur residues to be removed down to ppb level.

The purified fresh synthesis gas is mixed with the recycled gas from the FT reactor and, after being pre-heated, is fed to the FT reactor. In the FT reactor, the exothermal hydrocarbon chains producing reactions (R1) take place, while the produced heat is extracted by producing steam.

R1

The two-phase reactor product of FT synthesis consisting of water, hydrocarbons and non-reacted synthesis gas is cooled stepwise against recycle gas and cooling water in downstream heat exchangers. The liquid hydrocarbons, the condensing hydrocarbons and water in the mixture are separated from the gaseous compounds in intermediate flash vessels. The gas phase leaving the final separator mainly consists of light hydrocarbons, non-reacted synthesis gas and inert gases accumulated in the recycle gas. By purging a small part of the recycled gas, the overconcentration of inert gases to the FT reactor is avoided. Moreover, because of the low methane content in the fresh syngas, now steam methane reformer is needed to avoid the overconcentration of light hydrocarbons within the recycling loop.

The resulting blend of hydrocarbons is a crude product, hereinafter called as FT-crude, which can be forwarded to either co-processing or hydrotreating for further processing towards drop-in fuel synthesis. A dedicated hydrotreating and refining section has not been considered for the present analysis.

3 Heat & Mass balance calculations at steady-state conditions

The steady-state simulations of the plant are the foundations of the dynamic model. The steady-state model, within this study, is a result of an upscaling process of the TU Darmstadt pilot facilities. In 2015, a fluidized bed reactor was expanded with ThyssenKrupp Industrial Solutions so that a High-Temperature Winkler (HTW) gasification system can be tested [29, 30]. Thus, the investigation of stable operating conditions with inhomogeneous residual waste as feedstock can be carried out. As part of the Lig2Liq project, SRF and lignite were co-gasified in four testing campaigns. In addition, the TU Darmstadt expanded the pilot plant to include gas treatment for synthesis gas in 2020. In a mobile test rig provided by RWE, the complete process chain from gasification to synthesis can be demonstrated [31]. The pilot-scale HTW gasifier has a diameter of 400 mm and has a thermal input of up to 500 kW. The entire synthesis gas can be conditioned by gas treatment. The gas is first dedusted and a raw gas scrubber separates chlorides and partially ammonia and heavier tars. In order to reduce the capital expenses of gas conditioning on an industrial scale, the acid gas removal is based on a configuration including amine solvent [32]. For the removal of volatile organic components, a biodiesel (FAME) scrubber is installed upstream. FAME offers advantages for the removal of aromatics such as benzene, toluene, and xylene (BTX) like high solubility and thermal stability. This setup has been adapted from the treatment of coke oven gas to syngas processing [33].

The validated model of the pilot scale is the basis for the upscaling of the process. For gas cleaning and fuel synthesis, the upscaling of the pilot plant to ~800 MW-scale is possible. The industrial-scale gasifier was designed using the findings of the pilot tests in Darmstadt and the demonstration plant in Berrenrath [34]. The raw synthesis gas was thus determined via a conversion reactor. The downstream gas processing was simulated in Aspen Plus. In the following, the steady-state simulations of the 50-50 % wt. lignite/SRF case were considered as the validation medium and reference point towards the dynamic model development. The feedstock characterization for the solid feedstock (lignite/SRF) involved in simulations is presented in Table 1.

Table 1. Feedstock characterization for used lignite/SRF

	lignite	SRF
proximate analysis (as received)	wt. %	wt. %
moisture	12.30	2.50
ash	16.90	14.40
volatiles	37.89	74.40
fixed carbon	32.91	8.70

ultimate analysis (ash free)	wt. %	wt. %
carbon	70.23	64.65
hydrogen	4.89	8.98
oxygen	22.85	23.15
nitrogen	0.87	0.72
sulfur	1.11	0.25
chlorine	0.04	2.26
Lower heating value [kJ/kg]	18116	23734

The Aspen Plus steady-state model is characterized by the accurate physical modeling of multiphase interactions. The equation of state of the gas phase is described by the Redlich-Kwong Soave equation. The complexity is appropriate due to the increased pressure of the gasifier and all following units. The calculation of the liquid phase's chemical equilibrium is more challenging. Acid/base reactions are driving forces of various separation processes, especially regarding absorption. For this reason, the most important chemical reactions are implemented in the liquid phase. In order to calculate the chemical potential of aqueous solutions including the formed electrolytes, Aspen Plus offers the electrolyte extension of the Non-Random Two Liquids equation (ELEC-NRTL) [35]. All necessary parameters are obtained from the Aspen Plus database. In the BTX-Removal section, volatile organic components dissolve in biodiesel. The multicomponent system is largely unexplored. Especially, for this reason, further experiments at the TU Darmstadt pilot plant are necessary to analyze temperature- and pressure-dependent solubility and for a regression model using Henry coefficients. The structure of the molecular segments represents the most important parameter in this separation process. Van der Waals forces are the most important intermolecular interactions for molecules without a strong dipole, so the usage of the UNIQUAC equation is appropriate [36]. All absorption columns have been simulated with the rate-based mode. The residence time and the liquid hold-up are determined by correlations of physical heat and mass transfer. Chemical reactions occur in the liquid phase. The boundary layer of the gas-liquid interphase is considered separately. Aspen Plus provides correlations for the fluid dynamics of column internals from different manufacturers. The export to Aspen Plus Dynamics for the subsequent dynamic simulations envisages the appropriate dimensioning of the involved columns of the Gas Cleaning & Conditioning unit, that are presented in Table 2:

Table 2. Dimensioning of the Gas Cleaning & Conditioning unit

Unit	Modelling Approach	Length (m)	Diameter (m)
Water scrubber	Radfrac packed column	25	4
BTX gas cooler	Radfrac packed column	20	4.5
BTX absorber	Radfrac packed column	30	4
BTX desorber	Radfrac packed column & bottom product reboiler	15	4.5
Amine scrubber	Radfrac packed column	50	4
Amine desorber	Radfrac packed column & bottom product reboiler	30	4.5

A stoichiometric reactor (RSTOIC) was used for the FT reactor coupled with a calculator block that was based on the Anderson-Schulz-Flory (ASF) distribution. The selected low temperature catalyst that is selected corresponds to a chain growth probability equal to 90%, favouring the formation of long-chain hydrocarbons according to ASF.

An overview of the main stream results, as resulted from the 50-50 % wt. lignite/SRF full-scale (790 MW thermal input) steady state simulations of the full plant (Figure 1) are presented in Table 3. An energy balance of the concept is illustrated in Figure 2 as well. Concerning the assessment of the latter, two critical performance indicators are introduced: i) Cold Gas Efficiency (CGE), which refers to the gasification efficiency and is the chemical energy contained in the product gas with respect to the energy contained in the initial solid fuel (thermal input) & ii) Energetic Fuel Efficiency (EFE), which refers

to the efficiency of the overall plant and is the fraction of the chemical energy in the initial feedstock that is transferred to the final fuels (FT-liquids).

Table 3. Steady-state stream results from the 50-50 wt. lignite/SRF full-scale simulations

Stream No.	1(a+b)	2(a+b)	3	4	5	5a	6	6a	7	8	
Description	Solid feedstock	Gasifier agents	Raw syngas (after cooling)	Water scrubber overhead	Shifted gas	Tar-free gas	Amine scrubber overhead	Acid gas	Fine-cleaned gas	FT liquids	
T in °C	20.00	450.00	430.00	173.00	240.00	30.00	40.00	30.00	230	150	
P in bara	1.00	38.00	35.00	34.70	30.20	30.00	29.90	1.40	28.4	27	
SRF t/h	68										
lignite t/h	68										
total kmol/h		4109.33	12534.94	13657.82	13656.89	11609.18	8385.49	3328.82	8385.41		
total kg/h	136000	99619.2	235378.1	272883.1	272805.1	234951.9	93284.2	143560	93281.18	27652.50	
					<i>kmol/h</i>						
H ₂		0.00	4044.70	4044.45	5402.17	5401.70	5401.23	0.47	5401.23		
CO		0.00	3870.53	3870.36	2512.64	2510.34	2508.04	2.30	2508.04		
CO ₂		0.00	2010.57	2009.82	3367.54	3366.28	163.94	3202.34	163.94		
CH ₄		0.00	291.38	291.37	291.37	291.34	291.31	0.03	291.31		
H ₂ O		2277.04	2178.13	3350.27	1991.62	16.42	20.68	100.87	20.68		
N ₂		0.18	0.18	0.18	0.18	0.18	0.18	0.00	0.18		
O ₂		1832.10	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00		
H ₂ S		0.00	21.33	21.31	23.67	22.88	0.07	22.82	0.00		
COS		0.00	2.37	2.37	0.01	0.01	0.01	0.00	0.00		
NH ₃		0.00	63.63	53.21	53.21	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00		
HCl		0.00	37.54	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00		
Benzene		0.00	12.14	12.11	12.11	0.01	0.01	0.00	0.01		
Naphthalene		0.00	2.43	2.38	2.38	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00		
C1-C4										367.18	
C5-C11										7304.89	
C12-C20										7695.59	
C21-Waxes										12284.84	

Figure 2. Steady-state energy balance from the 50-50 wt. lignite/SRF full-scale simulations

The hot raw synthesis gas leaves the gasifier at around 780-800 °C. The heat of the raw syngas is recovered in a boiler system producing medium pressure steam (38 bar) which can be directly used in the process. The generated steam along with oxygen deriving from ASU are further pre-heated (450 °C) for higher thermal efficiency prior entering the HTW unit as gasification agents (stream 2). The raw synthesis gas after the boiler system (cooling) is specified in stream 3. The most important parameters of the synthesis gas cleaning and conditioning are the H₂/CO ratio and the residual content of critical impurities substances in the syngas after the respective process step. After water scrubbing, the H₂/CO ratio is set to the desired value of 2 via CO-shift. The COS content drops below 1 ppm after hydrolysis. Similarly, the benzene content decreases below 1 ppm after BTX removal. In the acid gas removal unit, the H₂S content is reduced below

10 ppm and a CO₂ content of 2% is achieved. The final purification unit ensures complete desulphurization of the clean syngas that will enter the FT-synthesis unit, where the final product (FT liquids) is formed according to ASF.

The CGE of the gasifier is around 80%, while the thermal exploitation of the hot raw syngas accounts for around the rest 20%. The latter refers to the pre-heating demands of oxygen and steam (9.34%) that will be involved in the HTW gasification unit as well as the potential useful excess heat (8.86%) that can be utilized for further steam generation. Moreover, 1% heat losses of the total thermal input are envisaged within the HTW gasification unit. The heat losses of the Gas Cleaning & Conditioning unit are minor (4.35%), while the main heat losses of the process are observed in the FT-synthesis unit (31.08%) due to mainly the highly exothermic Fischer-Tropsch reactions and secondly the FT-tail gas (i.e. purge gas containing unreacted syngas components). Therefore, an EFE around 45% is achieved, meaning the fraction of thermal input that is found in the final product of the process (i.e. FT-crude).

4 Dynamic model development and methodology

The dynamic simulations of the plant are carried out with the assistance of the commercial software Aspen Plus Dynamics™ (APD). APD is a sub-component of the aspenONE® Engineering Suite that permits the time-dependent examination of the system via direct export of a steady-state simulation (Aspen Plus™) into dynamic mode. The transition from steady state to dynamic mode of operation may be supported by Aspen software, nevertheless there are some constraints related to several components and properties that are present in steady-state but are not supported by APD (e.g. solids involvement) and therefore have to be replaced or modified. The strategy that is followed in order to overcome this kind of barriers in each unit is described in more detail below.

The selection of the control strategy is based mainly on the maximum utilization of the available assets in order to maintain the plant performance within the appropriate and desirable range of operation via a secure and efficient way [12, 37]. These types of models, which have a high degree of heat/work integration and large recycle streams are more prone to interactions in a control loop along with reduced available manipulated variables. A layer of advanced PID controls (Ratio and Cascade) is implemented on top of the existing regulatory control. The controller tuning has been done using Ziegler-Nichols open method to ensure stability and robustness for the control system. The integration of the models takes place in Simulink/MATLAB environment.

4.1 Air separation Unit – Steady state, export to APD and control strategy

The present ASU model was developed and validated against literature [38]. The developed model predicts an oxygen stream of 99.50% by mole purity, a nitrogen stream of 98.40% by mole purity and argon of 97.5% by mole purity. The main components of the ASU are the air compression & refrigeration system, the High Pressure Column (HPC), the Low Pressure Column (LPC) as well as the Argon column. More details concerning the selected ASU operation conditions and the modelling procedure can be found in the Supplementary Information 1.

In the ASU, the condenser pressure of the HPC is remaining at the desired pressure by employing a PI controller to manipulate the condenser's heat duty. In addition, the condenser liquid level of both HPC and Argon column is processed by varying their top flowrate. The HPC and Argon columns sump liquid level is controlled by manipulating their bottoms rate. Likewise, for the LPC, the column pressure and sump level also use PI controllers to maintain the optimal conditions by varying the top and bottoms flowrate. In addition, each compressor component and heat exchanger has a PI controller in order to control its output pressure and temperature, respectively, by manipulating each duty. A standalone ASU is designed to operate in a way that maximizes the production rate.

For the ASU, being part of the whole plant, the main objective is to meet the gasifier's oxygen demand in a dynamically 'best' possible way without violating the operating constraints, such as lower purity limit of 0.9 oxygen mole-fraction. Since the ASU model is configured according to the 100% plant load design operation, the following supervisory control layer is proposed backed up by classical PI-based controllers (Supplementary Information 3):

1. The feed-to-oxygen ratio block uses the oxygen demand and its value as input signal to the required feed-air flowrate. This ratio is based on the steady-state of oxygen demand and feed-air flow rate.
2. The liquid-nitrogen-to-oxygen ratio block contains the oxygen demand and liquid nitrogen flow rate set point as the corresponding inputs and output signals.
3. Composition controller that maintains oxygen purity in the oxygen product stream by directly adjusting set point signals to cascaded feed-air flow rate controller of air.

It should be pointed out that, even though the main objective of the developed ASU is to feed the gasification plant with oxygen of high purity, appropriate controls are also included to maintain the purity of the other two output streams (i.e. nitrogen and argon) at the desired levels.

4.2 Gasification – Steady state, export to APD and control strategy

Gasification can be considered as the most challenging part of the dynamic model development, since the solid feedstock (lignite/SRF) that enters the HTW gasifier is not supported from APD. Therefore, the gasification feedstock should be modelled as a combination of conventional compounds able to adequately represent the exact solid feedstock composition in terms of mass and energy input. In particular, the feed streams are a mixture of C, H, O, S, N and H₂O, all defined as conventional compounds. The composition of them is determined from the ultimate analysis of the respective fuels (see Supplementary Information). The ash is modelled as an inert compound like Ca or Si. Moreover, as the enthalpy of this stream is not the same with the enthalpy of the original 'correct' solid fuel, the energy balance consistency is satisfied by adding an inlet heat stream with value of that difference. Hydrodynamics play a considerable role in the process performance. Like in the majority of detailed BFB gasification process models in the literature, Kunii-Levenspiel model for bubbling fluidized bed was employed [39, 40]. More information regarding the modelling details and the procedure that was followed for the development of an 'exportable to APD' gasification model can be found in the Supplementary Information 2. In addition, the three steady-state scenarios (i.e. lignite/SRF 80-20, 50-50, 20-80 % wt.) that were used for the validation of the developed gasification model that can be directly exported to APD can be found in the Supplementary Information 2 as well.

One of the main objectives of the proposed concept is the feedstock flexibility and the ability to alter the feedstock mixture of the gasifier (lignite/SRF) without jeopardizing the stability and efficiency of the overall value chain.

On the part of the gasifier, this is achieved by keeping the syngas production rate and quality as stable as possible by regulating the gasification agents flowrates (i.e. steam & oxygen). More specifically, a feed-back flow controller (PI) is applied in the produced gas in order to control the syngas quality and towards this direction to adjust the steam inlet flow. The syngas quality is measured in terms of Cold Gas Efficiency (CGE) and is attempted to kept constant at the initial set point (>80%) regardless of the feedstock variations. The oxygen inlet flow, respectively, is conformed in a way that the oxidation reactions will provide the required heat that ensures the willing temperature along with the adiabatic operation of the reactor [21, 41, 42].

The quick adaptation of the gasifier in the feedstock deviations and its ability to ensure a continuous and qualitative syngas production is a critical issue for the whole plant and the desired liquid fuel production. Of course, the different feedstock mixtures come up

with different contaminants (H_2S , HCl , NH_3 , tars) concentrations in the produced syngas that cannot be controlled from the gasifier, but instead the gas cleaning and conditioning operation has to get adapted accordingly.

4.3 Gas Cleaning & Conditioning – Steady state, export to APD and control strategy

The Gas Cleaning & Conditioning unit of the proposed concept consists of the water scrubber for HCl and partial NH_3 removal, the Water-Gas-Shift reactor for the achievement of the desired H_2/CO ratio, the COS hydrolysis, the BTX removal unit for tar removal, the amine section for acid gas removal and finally the final purification stage that ensures the appropriate gas cleaning before the fuel synthesis unit.

For a successful transition from the steady-state simulations of the gas cleaning section into the dynamic mode, some features of the steady model should be transformed to be compatible with Aspen Plus Dynamics™. While equilibrium columns were sufficient enough for the accurate simulation of water scrubber and BTX removal at steady state, rate-based columns that involve kinetic reactions were used to adequately simulate the complex chemical reactions that take place in the amine section. However, rate-based columns are not supported from Aspen Plus Dynamics™ environment and therefore equilibrium columns with adapted stage efficiencies were used for the amine scrubber and desorber in the dynamic mode. Moreover, an RPLUG reactor with kinetic-based input was used for the implementation of the WGS reaction, while complete hydrolysis of COS was assumed. For the gas cleaning unit, equipment sizing (columns) is required for the dynamic simulations [43].

As already mentioned, the gas that enters the fuel synthesis unit must follow some specifications. These specifications are met within the gas cleaning & conditioning unit of the plant. Therefore, the developed control system of this unit should ensure that the gas that will enter the fuel synthesis section covers all the envisaged requirements no matter what fluctuations occur in the raw syngas composition due to feedstock variations in the gasifier. The control schemes for the gas cleaning & conditioning units are presented in Supplementary Information 3.

In the water scrubber, complete removal of HCl along with partial removal of NH_3 and heavier tars are aimed. The temperature of the scrubber overhead should be kept constant above 150-160 °C, to avoid tars condensation due to the high operating pressures. The flowrate of the upstream is manipulated in order to control the overhead pressure and the level in the sump is controlled by the bottoms flow rate, while the freshwater inlet flow is adjusted according to the flow rate of the raw syngas via ratio control. Then, part of the gas enters the WGS reactor in order the desired H_2/CO ratio (of 2) to be achieved. A feed-back flow controller is set at the exit of the WGS reactor that tunes the WGS by-pass stream via a splitter prior the reactor. The reactor temperature (i.e. 350 °C) is kept stable in respect to its steady-state conditions by tuning the pre-heating temperature of the 'to-shift' part of the syngas.

Concerning the BTX unit, PI control of the overhead pressure and the level in the sump is performed for each involved column (BTX gas cooler, BTX absorber & BTX desorber). An additional controller is introduced for the level in the desorber drum. The water/wash oil solvent is adjusted in the flow rate of the raw syngas via ratio control, aiming to keep the benzene concentrations in the exit gas stream below 1 ppm and its temperature around 30 °C.

Finally, similar control strategy is adopted for the columns of the amine section. Controllers are integrated for overhead pressure, sump and drum level in the desorber. A feed-back flow controller regulates the amine solvent flow rate in the amine scrubber, in order the leaving syngas composition specifications to be continuously satisfied ($\text{CO}_2 < 2\% \text{ vol}$ & $\text{H}_2\text{S} < 1 \text{ ppm}$). The amine scrubber overhead temperature is set around 40

°C, while the regenerated amine solvent leaves the desorber regularly at around 120 °C by tuning the 'rich' solvent pre-heating temperature [44].

4.4 Fuel synthesis (FT synthesis) – Steady state, export to APD and control strategy

Compared to the former sub-units, the Fischer-Tropsch synthesis process is modelled in a more straight-forward way. It consists of two main parts, the CO hydrogenation for FT synthesis and the liquids products recovery. A Stoichiometric reactor (RSTOIC) is selected for the FT synthesis modelling. The products prediction is accomplished according to the Anderson-Schulz-Flory distribution. In particular, the low temperature catalyst specifications that have been set correspond to a chain growth probability equal to 90%. A gas conversion rate of 60% per pass has been assumed. The water gas shift activity is not significant and is neglected in the current design.

Since the control schemes of the gasification and the gas cleaning units operate in a way to ensure that the FT synthesis specifications (i.e. H₂/CO ratio, contaminants levels, etc.) are strictly and continuously followed, the switch on the feed gas is not significant. Consequently, the focus of the control strategy of the fuel synthesis unit is given to the maintenance of the desired FT reactor & separation vessels temperatures that will secure stable and consistent FT liquids production as well as effective FT liquids retrieval. The control scheme for the FT synthesis is presented in Supplementary Information 3.

4.5 Integration of the sub-models and overall simulation strategy

The current study also considers the integration of Aspen Plus Dynamics™ and MATLAB/Simulink to examine the performance of the integrated system. The Simulink interface enables an APD simulation to be used as a block within Simulink model. This integration offers the opportunity to combine the advantages of two different software, i.e. the advanced capabilities of APD in modelling chemical processes and the flexibility offered by MATLAB/Simulink in implementing plantwide control schemes.

Moreover, the MATLAB/Simulink environment supports the implementation of the two assisting calculators that continuously refresh the devolatilization and bed hydrodynamics according to feedstock variations in the gasification model and a calculator that updates the FT product yields distribution according to the inlet gas partial pressures. Once all the subsystems are added to Simulink, the control strategy process begins. In each subsystem which has Aspen Plus Dynamic model inside, two types of Matlab functions are introduced which are responsible for the control strategy of the integrated system. The first one is responsible for activating/triggering the feedstock and load transitions in the Aspen Dynamic model while the second one is responsible for the real time implementation of the calculators into the APD models.

5 Dynamic simulations results & discussion

The dynamic simulations were performed over an assumed period of continuous plant operation. Two modes (case scenarios) were investigated:

- **Feedstock transition:** Initially, the plant operates with an 80-20 % wt. feedstock mixture (lignite/SRF) and then the gradual transition to a 20-80 % wt. mixture is attempted. During this transition, the plant operation is stabilized for some hours also with a 50-50 % wt. mixture. The upper limits of the examined fuel blends (80-20 & 20-80) were selected since the model has not been validated against the respective steady state model from TUDA for other fuel blends (e.g. 100% WTA or 100% SRF cases).

- Load transition (ramp up/down): Initially, the plant operates at full-load and then the direct transition to a partial-load (i.e. 70%) operation is aimed with constant feedstock mixture of 80-20 % wt. (Lignite/SRF). The ramp up/down rate is 3% load/min. After balance of the plant and steady operation is achieved at partial-load for some hours, the ramp up towards full-load and the return to the initial conditions is performed.

In general, the primary scope of the selected approach is to investigate the response of the individual parts of the plant for feedstock & load variations and to prove the concept flexibility in terms of operation adaptability and performance stability.

5.1 Feedstock transition

5.1.1 Gasification

As mentioned, it is assumed that the examined period starts with a steady plant operation of 80-20 % wt. (Lignite/SRF) feedstock ratio. In particular, a solid feedstock mixture that contains 108800 kg/h of lignite and 27200 kg/h of SRF enters the gasifier and corresponds to a thermal input of 727 MW_{th}. Figure 3 illustrates the feedstock transition throughout the examined 24-hour period and the flow variations of the respective solid fuels.

Figure 3. Feedstock mixture transition throughout the examined 24-hour period

After a steady-operation mode of 4 hours, the feedstock mixture starts to change gradually. The supply of lignite in the gasifier decreases, while the supply of SRF increases respectively. A 50-50 % wt. feedstock mixture is achieved after 9 hours, where a new steady-operation mode is adopted for 5 hours. Then, further decrease of lignite and further increase of SRF continue until a 20-80 % wt. feedstock mixture to be formed after 19 hours of operation. The latter is the last steady-operation point of the examined period. While lignite fraction decreases at the blend feedstock composition, the thermal input of the gasifier slightly increases due to the higher energy content of SRF in comparison with lignite.

As previously mentioned, during these feedstock fluctuations, the steam and oxygen inlet flows of the gasifier are properly regulated via control to ensure the best possible process performance and syngas stability. The behavior of steam & oxygen inlet flows throughout the 24-hour period is shown in Figure 4a.

Figure 4. a) Transition of gasification agents (O_2 and steam) inlet flows and b) syngas composition throughout the examined 24-hour period

The gradually increasing share of SRF in the feedstock mixture indicates a reduction of steam and oxygen inlet flows in order to keep the gasification performance at the desired level ($CGE > 80\%$). The gasification performance reflects to the produced syngas flow rate and composition that is presented in Figure 4b.

The focus is paid on the main syngas components (i.e. H_2 , CO , CO_2 , CH_4). A relatively consistent syngas quality is achieved throughout the 24-hour period despite the feedstock variations. The fact that the feedstock transition from lignite to SRF is performed gradually, by avoiding sharp and abrupt changes, has impact on the gasifier's balanced operation. Of course, this happens with the appropriate adjustment of steam and oxygen inlet flows, but sharp variations in the feedstock mixture would surely complicate the gasifier's response and put in danger the control of the process in terms of performance.

The H_2 content of the produced syngas ranges between 32-35 % vol. during the 24-hour session, the CO content between 30-32 % vol., the CO_2 between 13-19 % vol. and the CH_4 between 1.5-3 % vol. The relative stability of the syngas quality is translated also to stability of the gasification performance. The latter can be measured with the assistance of CGE , which is defined as the ratio of the chemical energy content of the produced syngas to the thermal input of the gasifier. The slight fluctuation of CGE throughout the 24 hours is presented in Figure 5.

Figure 5. Cold Gas Efficiency (CGE) transition throughout the examined 24-hour period

The applied gasification control achieves to keep CGE above the threshold value ($> 80\%$) during the whole session. It may momentarily reach values slightly below 80% during feedstock transition, but it returns very quickly (< 0.25 h) and stabilizes in the desired state. In general, the consistency of CGE illustrates the efficient control of the gasification process that opens the way for a reliable plant performance for flexible feedstock.

5.1.2 Air Separation Unit

The main objective of the ASU control is to cover the oxygen requirements of the gasifier in terms of the gasifier in terms of purity and quantity throughout the process (Figure 6a). In general, ASU presence acts as a limitation to transient phenomena and ramp rates for oxy-gasification plants due to its inability to directly synchronize its oxygen production with sharp deviations in the gasifier demand. This can be overcome by the integration of liquid oxygen storage forms (e.g. buffer tank) into the control system for oxygen supply to the gasification unit [45]. The rationale is to store any excessive ASU oxygen production and activate it during transient phenomena, where ASU seems unable to provide instantly the required oxygen.

Figure 6. a) Gasification oxygen demand accomplishment via Air Separation Unit and b) ASU outlet oxygen, nitrogen and argon purities

The ASU ensures the required oxygen quantities are provided, during the examined period, because the oxygen demand decreases through each transition. Any excess produced oxygen can be stored in oxygen storage tanks. Apart from oxygen production for gasification utilization, nitrogen and argon streams of high purity are also outputs of the air separation process (Figure 6b). Their inert properties are commonly exploited in various applications of other industries (metal/steel industries, electronics, etc.).

5.1.3 Gas Cleaning & Conditioning

Apart from the effect of the feedstock transition on the syngas quality in terms of H_2 , CO , CO_2 , CH_4 deviations, another crucial aspect that should be taken into consideration is the effect in terms of contaminants and impurities that each feedstock contains. For example, the sulphur (S) content of lignite is higher than the sulphur content of SRF, while the chlorine (Cl) content of SRF is higher than the respective content of lignite. Therefore, the HCl and H_2S concentrations of syngas vary along with the feedstock and their production is not defined by the gasifier, but from their initial content in the feedstock. Moreover, tars (e.g. benzene) or ammonia (NH_3) are also species with variable concentrations during the session that must be removed from the gas before the fuel synthesis unit.

The role of the gas cleaning & conditioning unit is to continuously provide the fuel synthesis unit with a clean gas that meets all the specifications independently of the feedstock fluctuations that take place in the gasifier. This means that the operation of the individual processes of this unit (Water Scrubber, Gas-Shift, BTX, Amine section) needs to quickly get adapted to the produced syngas cleaning requirements.

The first part of the gas cleaning & conditioning configuration refers to the water scrubber. Within this section, the syngas is cooled down up to a point while some of the syngas contaminants, mainly HCl, are removed. The temperature of the scrubber overhead is around 170 °C and should be kept at this level in order to avoid tars

condensation. The efficient removal of the HCl along with the maintenance of the desired temperature in the scrubber via the freshwater flow are presented in Figure 7.

Figure 7. a) Efficient HCl removal and b) maintenance of the scrubber temperature throughout the examined 24-hour period

Afterwards, the cooled syngas enters the Water-Gas Shift (WGS) section, where the adjustment of the desired H_2/CO molar ratio is carried out. In particular, only a part of syngas takes part in the WGS reaction, while a by-pass gas stream is mixed with the shifted gas downstream the shift reactor. The split of the gas prior the reactor into by-pass stream and reactor feed stream is performed according to the control of the H_2/CO ratio in the exit of the section.

The mole flows of the syngas components that are involved in the WGS reaction (i.e. H_2 , CO , CO_2) prior and after the WGS section are presented in Figure 8a. In Figure 8b, it is shown the maintenance of the H_2/CO output molar ratio (~ 2) as well as the required by-pass stream percentage tuning prior the reactor for its accomplishment.

Figure 8. a) $H_2/CO/CO_2$ mole flows prior and after the WGS section, b) Maintenance of the desired H_2/CO (~ 2) molar ratio and by-pass WGS stream percentage

The desired H_2/CO is controlled quite smoothly without sharp deviations in the by-pass stream percentage. This happens due to the similar syngas quality that reaches the WGS section throughout the 24-hour period and is a result of the effective control that takes place in the gasification unit. Only minor adaptations around 60% are required for the by-pass WGS stream, having as a result an almost-steady behavior of the system in the desired conditions, which is positive. It should be underlined that no further addition of steam is required, since the water content of the saturated gas that leaves the water scrubber is enough to fulfil the WGS requirements.

Then, the shifted syngas enters the BTX removal unit. The main produced tar component to be removed is benzene, but within this unit, the complete removal of the remaining ammonia as well as of naphthalene is also performed. The aim that has been set is to keep benzene concentrations below 1 ppm after the BTX removal unit (Figure 9). The

water/wash oil solvent flow is adjusted in order to ensure the desired operating conditions, while the temperature of the BTX absorber overhead is kept at 30 °C.

Figure 9. Ammonia & Benzene concentrations in the gas after BTX removal unit

The tar-free gas is directed to the major part of the gas cleaning value chain, which is the amine section. Within this section, CO₂ & H₂S (acid gas) removal is performed. In particular, CO₂ (Figure 10a) and H₂S (Figure 10b) are captured, via chemical reactions that take place in the amine scrubber, aiming to reduce the CO₂ & H₂S content of the clean syngas below 2% vol. and 1 ppm respectively.

In the amine desorber, the captured acid gas is stripped from the amine solvent and leaves the column from the top while the regenerated amine solvent leaves the desorber at the bottom (Figure 11a). A make-up amine stream that corresponds to ~0.1% of the lean solvent is mixed with the regenerated solvent before the latter to be sent to the absorber top. The temperature of the amine scrubber overhead (clean syngas) is controlled at ~40 °C, while the reboiler temperature in the desorber (regenerated solvent) operates at ~120 °C (Figure 11a). The acid gas, obtained in the top of the desorber, mainly consists of CO₂ (Figure 11b). Pure CO₂ can be extracted from the acid gas after applying desulfurization methods.

Figure 10. Efficient CO₂ (a) and H₂S (b) removal and capture throughout the examined 24-hour period

Figure 11. a) Lean & regenerated MDEA solvent and controlled temperature of amine scrubber's top and desorber's bottom, b) CO₂ & H₂S concentrations in the captured acid gas throughout the examined 24-hour period

The clean gas that exits the amine section will be used as feed gas to the downstream fuel synthesis unit. Before its direction to the Fischer-Tropsch section, the gas passes from a final purification stage (e.g. ZnO guard bed) where remaining sulphur residues are removed down to ppb level. This part of the gas cleaning section has not been considered for the present dynamic analysis.

5.1.4 FT synthesis

The FT-crude production, which is the final product of the presented value chain and the most important performance indicator of the plant, remains stable among 26800-28500 kg/h (Figure 12a). The small increase in productivity is due to the increasing involvement of SRF throughout the examined period, which is equal to increasing thermal input in the gasifier.

Figure 12. FT-crude production (a) and yields composition (b) throughout the examined 24-hour period

The final product yield of the plant (kg FT-crude / kg feedstock), and consequently the overall performance, is kept constant throughout the feedstock transition and in particular in the range of ~19-21 %. This can be shown also from the achieved general stability of EFE (44-48%) throughout the examined period (Figure 13a).

Figure 13. a) EFE throughout the examined 24-hour period, b) Isothermal FT reactor operation and produced heat throughout the examined 24-hour period

The FT product yields distribution (Figure 12b) also remains stable as a consequence of the control that is applied in the synthesis conditions and includes the constant H_2/CO ratio (~ 2) of the inlet gas as well as the isothermal FT reactor operation ($\sim 220^\circ C$) via extraction of the produced heat by steam cycle (Figure 13b).

5.2 Load transition (ramp up/down)

5.2.1 Gasification

In this mode, the transition of the plant in partial-load and its return to full-load conditions with constant feedstock mixture is examined. The current accepted ramping capability for syngas plants is considered to be $\sim 3\%$ load/min. Ramping up at rates over 2-3% per minute enters a serious risk of losing syngas quality and since in chemical plants there is generally no incentive to increase the ramp beyond this, in contrast with power plants, operators tend to be conservative with ramp rates and load variations as well. Moreover, while in power plants syngas quality deviations can be handled as an undesirable situation, in chemical plants can lead to even immediate shutdown of the chemical synthesis unit (e.g. catalyst poisoning) [45].

Considering all the above mentioned points, starting from a steady full-load plant operation (4 hours), it is attempted the ramp down and operation of the plant at 70% load for the next 4 hours and finally the ramp up and return to full-load conditions (Figure 14a). The ramp up/down rate is $\pm 3\%$ load/min while feedstock mixture of the gasifier remains constant throughout the load variations and equal to 80-20 % wt. (Lignite/SRF). The aimed stability of the syngas quality and consequently the CGE of the gasification unit is the flexibility indicator of the plant. The CGE at partial-load operation may be slightly lower in comparison with the base-load operation, but it should be kept around the desired level. The CGE fluctuation during the examined period is presented in Figure 14b. It is observed that apart from the light deviations during the almost instantaneous load transition, gasification efficiency is kept constant and the response time (< 0.5 h) fast enough.

Figure 14. a) Load transition throughout the examined 12-hour period, b) Load transition impact on Cold Gas Efficiency (CGE)

The main objective during load fluctuations is the maintenance of the syngas quality. This is achieved with the timely adjustment of the oxygen and steam inlet flows of the gasifier. In particular, the oxygen/carbon (O/C) ratio and consequently the stability of the operation temperature is regulated via oxygen, while the syngas composition consistency is controlled via steam. Since steam is generated from recovered heat through syngas cooling, the fluctuations in steam demands are not feasible to be met unless a steam storage tank is considered. Otherwise, a lag in the desired steam flow that enters the gasifier is expected. The response of the gasification agents as well as the controlled syngas quality during load transition are presented in Figure 15.

Figure 15. a) Syngas main species flow rates throughout the examined 12-hour period (flow-based) b) Feedstock mixture and Steam & oxygen inlet flows adjustment throughout the load transition

5.2.2 Air Separation Unit

The Air Separation Unit is unable to timely 'follow' the oxygen requirements of the gasifier due to the instantaneous load transition (Figure 16). Integrating oxygen storage into the control system for oxygen supply to the gasification unit can overcome this limitation.

Figure 16. ASU oxygen production and sync with gasifier throughout the load transition

During ramp-down, excess oxygen is generated due to the slow response time of ASU. This excess oxygen cannot enter the gasifier, since it will disrupt the desired and controlled gasification operating conditions by excessive oxidation of valuable components (i.e. CO & H₂). Instead, it can be stored in a dedicated buffer tank that will be able to bridge the reverse gap between ASU production and gasifier demand, when ASU struggles to provide timely the increased ramp-up oxygen requirements.

5.2.3 Gas Cleaning & Conditioning

The maintenance of the standard syngas quality, that is achieved in the gasification unit, facilitates the smooth adaptation of the gas cleaning & conditioning unit as well. Initially, the produced gas is cooled down in the water scrubber with appropriate adjustment of the freshwater flow and then enters the WGS section for the H₂/CO ratio (~2) tuning (Figure 17).

Figure 17. H₂, CO, CO₂ flows prior and after WGS section throughout load transition

The main concern regarding the adaptability of the gas cleaning & conditioning unit in load fluctuations, is the constant efficient removal of contaminants and acid gas. In particular, an almost instantaneous rump down can be managed without loss of gas cleaning efficiency. However, ramping up at high rates (>3%/min) can be dangerous for the process sustainability, since time is required for the solvents re-adjustment (e.g. water/wash oil, amines) and potential contaminants breakthrough can lead to immediate shutdown of the plant.

The impact of load transition on the removal of benzene, CO₂ and H₂S is presented in Figure 18.

Figure 18. a) Impact of load transition on benzene removal after BTX b) Impact of load transition on CO₂ removal after amine scrubber c) Impact of load transition on H₂S removal after amine scrubber throughout the examined 12-hour period

With the ramp rate ($\pm 3\%/min$) that was applied within the present load-varying simulations, it can be observed that efficient removal of the targeted components is performed throughout the examined period and their concentrations are kept steadily below the clean gas threshold values (i.e. benzene < 1 ppm, CO₂ $< 2\%$ vol.). For the H₂S, the risk of sulphur breakthrough is managed not only from the amine section quick response, but also from a final purification stage (e.g. ZnO guard bed) where remaining sulphur residues are removed down to ppb level.

In general, at high ramp up rates, instantaneous lower removal efficiency is presented, rendering a critical point where contaminants concentration is momentarily above the steady operation. This happens because of the time required for the cleaning solvents to be adjusted and attention should be given that this point will not exceed the threshold values when even higher ramp up rates are applied.

5.2.4 FT synthesis

The isothermal operating conditions of FT-synthesis and consequently the quality of fuel production are attempted to remain stable during load transition (Figure 19). Due to the fast load change, small deviations are observed in the reactor temperature, but not enough to affect the production quality. It has to be mentioned that the control of the FT reactor temperature during load transition is a quite challenging task compared to the feedstock transition mode, since sharp deviations in the syngas flow that enters the FT-reactor may cause the reactor run away. Figure 19b presents affordable temperature deviations during transition to 70% load operation, but during more intense ramp up/down tests that were carried out (e.g. 60% load operation) within the present study, FT-reactor proved unable to recover and keep the desired operating condition intact.

The FT-crude production decreases, as expected, with the load reduction. The final product yield of the plant (kg FT-crude / kg feedstock) remains constant in the range of ~19-21% also for partial-load plant operation (Figure 19c) as well as the *EFE* consistently over 45% (Figure 19d).

Figure 19. a) FT-crude production throughout load transition and b) FT reactor temperature and produced heat throughout load transition c) FT-yield throughout load transition, d) Energetic fuel efficiency throughout load transition

6 Conclusions

Within this work, dynamic simulations of a HTW gasification plant for Fischer-Tropsch liquids production were performed and the response of the plant in feedstock transition as well as in load transition (ramp up/down) were assessed. The proof of concept in dynamic mode was accomplished and the identification of key aspects of the process that need to be controlled in order the system to counteract the feedstock/load deviations was carried out. Initially, gradual variation of the lignite/SRF feedstock mixture at full-load was examined, and then instant ramp down at partial-load operation and instant ramp up return to full-load conditions with constant feedstock mixture were applied. Dynamic simulations revealed that the plant performance can be maintained at the desired design levels not only during the transition on fuel blend but also during the plant's load variation. The gasifier is able to keep the CGE at high rates (>80%) in all the examined cases. The achieved EFE of the concept is kept well above 40% in every examined transition as well. ASU is the only unit that presents slow response in the variations of oxygen demands but this can be addressed with the installation of a buffer tank. All the compartments of the gas cleaning section demonstrate efficient removal of the targeted components and keep them below the specified thresholds. The load transition runs were performed at 70% load. FT-reactor run away was observed during ramp up/down conditions below 60% load, but in such chemical plants there is usually no incentive of such intense ramping rates and load variations.

The proposed value chain seems to have a respectable potential in terms of operation adaptability and performance stability, always concerning the gasification-based chemical plants and the constraints that accompany them. It has to be mentioned that the main objective of the performed dynamic simulations was the proof of concept flexibility in unsteady conditions, rather than the optimization of the applied control scheme and optimal dynamic response of the system in terms of techno-economic efficiency. A more sophisticated control scheme in specific parts of the value chain as well as a more in-depth parametric analysis towards dealing with difficult situations like

equipment failure can be applied in future work. The correlation of the latter with the techno-economic efficiency can be re-evaluated with the further maturation of the technology and could potentially be a follow-up work.

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Supplementary Information 1

ASU dynamic (exportable to APD) model description

Air refrigeration

Ambient air (78% N₂, 20.96% O₂, 0.93% Ar vol.) is used as input stream in the separation process. A series of four compressors are increasing the pressure of the incoming air stream to 6 bar. The normal boiling point of nitrogen and oxygen are 77K and 90K respectively. This means that the air afterwards must be cooled down as much as possible to very low temperatures for the separation to take place. The compressed air is split and about 10% is compressed even more, cooled and passed through an expander. The work produced by the expander is used to drive the compressor.

High Pressure Column (HPC)

The main air feed which is cooled down at a temperature of -172 °C enters the HP column. This column separates nitrogen from argon and oxygen, producing at the overhead, pure liquid nitrogen. This product has a purity of 99.7% by mole nitrogen. The flowrate of the bottom product from the HP column is 55% of the feed rate and it contains about 39.1% oxygen, 1.4% argon with the remainder being nitrogen.

Low Pressure Column (LPC)

The LP column operates at about 1.5 bar and separates the nitrogen and oxygen to give high purity products of each. The overhead product is gaseous nitrogen with the same purity as the liquid nitrogen product from the HP column. Both liquids and gaseous oxygen are drawn from the bottom of the column. The oxygen product stream will be of higher purity than 99.5%, because the argon is removed from the side draw. The main oxygen feed to the LP column is the bottom from the HP column. It is subcooled by exchange with the low pressure nitrogen product and is used to provide cooling in the argon column condenser. The air from the turbo-expander is fed a few trays below the main feed. The reflux in the LP column is supplied by the liquid nitrogen product from HP column. This stream is subcooled by exchange with the low pressure nitrogen product and flashed through a valve.

Argon Column

The Argon column feed is a vapor side draw from the bottom section of the LP column and the argon vapor is removed overhead. Because nitrogen is more volatile than argon, it is essential that the feed contains very little nitrogen. In order to ensure this, the draw from the LP column is taken a few trays below the maximum argon concentration. The draw rate is about 20% of the air feed rate to the plant and only about 4% of the draw stream is removed as argon product.

Supplementary Information 2

Gasification dynamic (exportable to APD) model description and validation

Information such as fluidization agent characteristics (U , μ), gas/solids density (ρ_g , ρ_p), particles mean diameter (d_p), reactor main dimensions (D , H_t , A_t), perforations and solids inventory (W), are used as input in order to calculate the bed height (h_f), dense zone/freeboard volume area, solid volume fraction distribution as well as the bubble/emulsion phase volume ratio (δ).

The minimum fluidization velocity is calculated as [39]:

$$U_{mf} = \frac{d_p^2(\rho_p - \rho_g)g}{1650\mu} \quad \text{Equation 1}$$

The bed height is estimated as [46]:

$$h_f = h_{mf} \left[1 + \frac{10.978(U - U_{mf})^{0.738} d_p^{1.006} \rho_p^{0.376}}{U_{mf}^{0.937} \rho_g^{0.126}} \right] \quad \text{Equation 2}$$

where, U is the superficial velocity and:

$$h_{mf} = \frac{W}{A_t(1 - \varepsilon_{mf})(\rho_p - \rho_g)} \quad \text{Equation 3}$$

The volume fraction of the bed consisting of bubbles (δ) is defined as:

$$\delta = \frac{U - U_{mf}}{U_b - U_{mf}} \quad \text{Equation 4}$$

where the relative bubble velocity (U_b) is calculated as following [47]:

$$U_b = 0.71(gd_b)^{1/2} + (U - U_{mf}) \quad \text{Equation 5}$$

The bubble diameter (d_b) is calculated from the following equation [48]:

$$\frac{d_{bm} - d_b}{d_{bm} - d_{b0}} = e^{-0.3h_f/D} \quad \text{Equation 6}$$

where the maximum bubble diameter (d_{bm}) and the initial bubble diameter (d_{b0}) are respectively:

$$d_{bm} = 0.652 \left[\frac{\pi}{4} D^2 (U - U_{mf}) \right]^{0.4} \quad \text{Equation 7}$$

$$d_{b0} = 0.347 \left[\frac{\pi}{4} D^2 \left(\frac{U - U_{mf}}{N_d} \right) \right]^{0.4} \quad \text{Equation 8}$$

As concerns the reaction mechanism, it is split into two steps, the devolatilization and the gasification step. The devolatilization step is modelled as instantaneous (without time effect) and the remaining char is modelled as C instead of $C_aH_bO_c$. Representation in the form of $C_aH_bO_c$ could not work as the feedstock composition varies when the lignite/SRF fraction changes and the selected components along with their properties must be defined a priori in Aspen Plus™. H & O that do not participate in the char formation remain in gaseous form, respecting thus the elemental balance:

where [49]:

$$x_{CO} = 0.000417 \cdot T - 0.326 \quad \text{Equation 9}$$

$$x_{CO_2} = 0.0000327 \cdot T + 0.0303 \quad \text{Equation 10}$$

$$x_{CH_4} = 0.0000119 \cdot T + 0.011 \quad \text{Equation 11}$$

$$x_{char} = -0.000458 \cdot T + 1.23 \quad \text{Equation 12}$$

$$x_{C_6H_6} = 0.42 \cdot (1 - \sum x_i) \quad \text{Equation 13}$$

$$x_{C_{10}H_8} = 0.37 \cdot (1 - \sum x_i) \quad \text{Equation 14}$$

$$x_{C_6H_6} = 0.21 \cdot (1 - \sum x_i) \quad \text{Equation 15}$$

$$x_C = x_{C,tot} - \sum C \text{ contained in other products} \quad \text{Equation 16}$$

$$x_{H_2} = x_{H,tot} - \sum H \text{ contained in other products} \quad \text{Equation 17}$$

$$x_{O_2} = x_{O,tot} - \sum O \text{ contained in other products} \quad \text{Equation 18}$$

For the impurities synthesis, the following reactions are assumed:

In the gasification step, it is assumed that only homogeneous reactions take place in the bubble and freeboard zone whereas in the emulsion zone both homogeneous and heterogeneous reactions are considered:

Homogeneous reactions

Heterogeneous reactions

After applying the provided input parameters of each case (i.e. feedstock, steam & oxygen flows), the alignment of the results concerning the produced syngas estimation was assessed and presented below. In Figure 20, Figure 21, Figure 22, (where 'Steady' are the numbers from the steady state simulations (see section 3) and 'Dynamic' are the respective numbers from the developed dynamic model under steady conditions).

Figure 20. Developed dynamic gasification model validation for the 80-20 scenario

Figure 21. Developed dynamic gasification model validation for the 50-50 scenario

Figure 22. Developed dynamic gasification model validation for the 20-80 scenario

It can be observed that the dynamic model is in good agreement with the prediction of the main syngas components (H₂, CO, CO₂, CH₄), the contaminants (H₂S, NH₃, HCL) as well as the tars (C₆H₆, C₁₀H₈) formation in all three steady state scenarios. Therefore, it can be considered as a reliable tool for the subsequent dynamic simulations of the concept.

Supplementary Information 3
Process Flowsheet Diagrams (PFD) for the sub-units of the process chain and main controllers setup

Figure 23. Air Separation Unit (ASU)

Figure 24. HTW gasification unit

Figure 25. Gas Cleaning & Conditioning

Figure 26. FT-synthesis unit

Table 4. Key controllers setup

PI Controller	Unit	Set Point	Process Variable	Output
CCO2_RAT	ASU	99.5 % vol.	Purity of O2 in the exit of the LPC	Feed-air /oxygen demand ratio (kmol/kmol)
OX_FLOW	Gasification	790 °C	Temperature of the hot raw synthesis gas at the gasifier exit	Oxygen flowrate (kmol/h)
ST_FLOW	Gasification	>80%	Cold Gas Efficiency (CGE)	Steam flowrate (kmol/h)
SC_WFLOW	Gas Cleaning & Conditioning	170 °C	Temperature of the water scrubber overhead	Raw syngas/fresh water ratio (kmol/kmol)
H2/CO_RAT	Gas Cleaning & Conditioning	2.00	H2/CO molar ratio at the exit of the WGS reactor	WGS by-pass stream (%)
WOIL	Gas Cleaning & Conditioning	< 1 ppm	Benzene concentration in BTX absorber overhead	Shifted gas/wash oil solvent (kmol/kmol)
AM_SOLV	Gas Cleaning & Conditioning	<2% vol.	CO2 concentration in the amine scrubber overhead	Tar free gas/amine solvent (kmol/kmol)
ACID_G	Gas Cleaning & Conditioning	>95% vol.	CO2 concentration in the amine desorber overhead (acid gas)	Amine desorber reflux ratio (kmol/kmol)
FT_TEMP	FT- synthesis	220 °C	FT reactor temperature	Steam flow (FT-reactor released heat) (kmol/h)